

A rapid and simple HPLC method for the routine laboratory analysis of Sudan (I to IV) dyes in chilli and chilli products

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Abstract : A reversed-phase liquid chromatography method was developed for the separation, identification and quantification of Sudan I, II, III and IV in chilli powder and chilli-based pickles and sauces. Sudan dyes, after extraction from the products using chloroform, were analyzed using C18 column, acetonitrile-water gradient mixture as eluent and variable wavelength detector at 491 nm. Their individual detection limit was in the range of 0.18 µg/ml to 0.19 µg/ml and recovery was 90 to 106%. Application and suitability of this method for routine analysis is demonstrated.

Keywords : Sudan, chilli, chloroform, acetonitrile, liquid chromatography, gradient elution.

Sudan dyes are red dyes that are used for coloring solvents, oils, waxes, petrol and shoe and floor polish. However their presence has been reported in certain hot chilli products, and has become an issue of public health concern in many countries. Sudan dyes (Fig. 1) are considered to be genotoxic carcinogens and recently their presence at any level is not permitted in food stuffs for any purpose. They also form DNA adducts with human DNA in specifically engineered human liver cells¹. Sudan I has been classified as a category 3 carcinogen by the IARC (International Agency for Research on Cancer).

As a consequence of the non-compliance of the presence of this contaminant in hot chilli and hot chilli products with the EU food safety requirements, in June 2003 the European Commission has adopted a decision on emergency measures concerning hot chilli and chilli products intended for human consumption and on January 2004 the EU food regulations 2003 decided to extend the commission decision 2003/460/EC requirement to cover Sudan II, Sudan III and Sudan IV^{1,2}. Methods are available for the determination of synthetic colours in foods using HPLC techniques^{3,4}. A few methods have been already reported for the determination of Sudan I in chillies⁵⁻⁸. Tateo and Bonani⁹ have reported a method for the determination of Sudan I by HPLC coupled with AP-MS (Atmospheric Pressure Chemical Ionisation-Mass Spectrometry) detection. Recently a few methods have been published for the simultaneous determination of Sudan I to IV¹⁰⁻¹³. These methods are based on ESI-Q-

Fig. 1. Structure of Sudan dyes.

TOF MS (Electrospray Ionization-Quadrupole-Time of Flight Mass Spectrometry) and LC-ESI-MS/MS (Liquid Chromatography-Electrospray Ionization-Tandem Mass Spectrometry) techniques etc., but there are no simple and rapid HPLC methods available for the simultaneous determination of Sudan dyes in chilli products which all the laboratories can afford. The need for such a method is felt in the present scenario, since some chilli based products are adulterated with Sudan I and Sudan IV in combination. The objective of this study is to develop a method for the separation, identification and quantification of oil soluble colours, viz. Sudan I, II, III and IV in chillies and chilli products. The method is also validated for its accuracy, precision, limit of detection and limit of quantification, so that it can be applied for a routine analysis in the laboratories.

Experimental

Chemicals :

Sudan I, Sudan II, Sudan III and Sudan IV standards were obtained from Acros Organics, USA, chloroform (HPLC grade), acetonitrile (HPLC grade) and anhydrous sodium sulfate (A.R.) from Merck Limited, Mumbai, India. All solutions were prepared with water purified with a Milli-Q system (Millipore, Bedford, MA, USA).

HPLC analysis :

The analysis was performed on a Agilent model system (Agilent, 1100 series, Agilent Technologies Hong Kong Ltd., Taikoo shing, Hong Kong) equipped with an autosampler, binary pump and variable wavelength detector (double beam photometer 190–600 nm wavelength range and ± 1 wavelength accuracy). The dyes were detected using vwd set at 491 nm. A C18 μ Bondapak column (Waters India Ltd.), 3.98×300 mm, 10 microns was used at 25 °C temperature. The mobile phase A was water and B acetonitrile. The optimized binary gradient elution programme listed below was operated at a flow rate of 1.5 ml per minute.

	%A	%B
Initial	30	70
20 min	5	95

The mobile phase was filtered through 0.45 μ m filter and degassed prior to use.

Sample preparation :

Twelve samples of red chilli powder, pickles, tomato sauce and chilli sauce were analysed in this study. A few market samples which we had come across in our laboratory contained Sudan dyes in a concentration range of 50

to 400 μ g/ml. Hence this range of concentrations were chosen for the study. Samples of chilli and chilli products were accurately weighed and spiked at three different concentrations (50 μ g/ml, 100 μ g/ml and 250 μ g/ml) of Sudan I to IV, mixed homogeneously. Excess of solvent was added to the spiked samples and mixed well with the glass rod, then the solvent was evaporated in a rotary vacuum evaporator to allow thorough mixing of the sample with the dye.

Procedure :

Weigh accurately 5 g of the sample, add 70 ml chloroform. Shake for 45 min in the mechanical shaker. Filter into a 100 ml volumetric flask through anhydrous Na₂SO₄. Wash thoroughly with the solvent until all colour is extracted. Make up to the mark. Filter through 0.45 μ m filter and inject to HPLC. For samples which contain less than 10 μ g/ml of Sudan dyes, weight of sample and dilution may be changed accordingly. In such cases, 10 g of sample may be extracted with chloroform and diluted to 25 ml volume. Concentration of the dye in the sample is calculated directly from the calibration curve, by putting appropriate dilution factors.

HPLC method validation : Validation tests were performed for accuracy, precision, linearity, limit of detection and limit of quantification. The accuracy of the method was evaluated by recovery where each Sudan dye in concentrations of 50 μ g/ml, 100 μ g/ml and 250 μ g/ml were spiked in samples and compared with blank. Each analysis was done in triplicates. The sample solutions were properly diluted to fit in the calibration range and the percentage recovery was calculated. The precision of the method was evaluated by repeatability, intermediate precision and reproducibility. It is expressed by standard deviation and relative standard deviation. One-way ANOVA and homogeneity variance were also performed for statistical confirmation of repeatability and reproducibility. The linearity of the method was evaluated by injecting 20 μ l of the mixture of standards of Sudan I to IV at 0.2 μ g/g to 20 μ g/g level (8 concentrations). Calibration curves were constructed individually by plotting peak areas versus concentrations. The limit of detection and limit of quantification of the method was determined following IUPAC guidelines¹⁴⁻¹⁶ using the equations

$$\text{LOD} = \frac{3.3 \text{ SD}}{s}$$

$$\text{LOQ} = \frac{10 \text{ SD}}{s}$$

where LOD is the limit of detection, LOQ is the limit of quantification, SD is the standard deviation of the y intercepts of the regression line and s is the slope of calibration curve.

Results and discussion

Preparation of proper mobile phase depends mainly on the analytes and on the complexity of the food matrix. In this study, we chose the solvent ratio of (30% water : 70% acetonitrile) as the starting chromatographic conditions for the analysis of mixture of Sudan I, II, III and IV. Slowly the concentration of acetonitrile was increased from 70 to 95% within 20 min so as to get a very good resolution of the peaks. Since the capacity factors of all analytes are sensitive to the composition of the mobile phase, great care and precision are required in its preparation. Following this, reproducible retention times were obtained. No separation was achieved at a flow rate of 0.8 ml/min. The flow rate of mobile phase was progressively increased until baseline resolution was achieved, this was found to be at a flow rate of 1.5 ml/min. Fig. 2 shows the HPLC profile of Sudan I, II, III and IV.

Fig. 2. HPLC chromatogram of Sudan I, II, III and IV, with variable wavelength detector at 491 nm and using C18 column. (MAU – Million Absorption Unit).

The choice of extracting solvent is also crucial in recovery experiments. Solvents like methanol, acetonitrile and chloroform were tried to extract the dyes from spiked samples. Methanol and acetonitrile were not giving satisfactory recoveries, hence chloroform was chosen as the extracting solvent. The wavelength of detection was taken an optimum value of 491 nm at which all the four Sudan dyes were found to absorb maximum.

HPLC method validation and performance : Method validation is an essential component of the measures that a laboratory should implement to allow it to produce reliable analytical data. Hence we have given importance to validation of the developed analytical method according to IUPAC guidelines¹⁴ evaluating the method for its accuracy, precision, recovery, detection limits, quantification limits, linearity, sensitivity and applicability.

The limit of detection for Sudan I, II, III and IV are 0.18 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 0.19 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 0.18 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 0.18 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ respectively, and the limit of quantification values are 0.55 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 0.57 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 0.55 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 0.55 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ respectively.

With the proposed chromatographic conditions all analytes showed good linearity between the concentrations and peak area responses. Repeating nine times the calibration of mixture of Sudan dyes, the standard deviation of slope, standard deviation of y intercepts and correlation factors of the regression line are given in Table 1. The standards were in a concentration range of 0.2 to 20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ (8 concentrations).

Table 1. Linearity of Sudan dyes

Analyte	Regression equation	S.D. of slope	S.D. of y intercept	Correlation factor ($n = 8$)
Sudan I	$Y = 5.55X + 0.29$	0.18	0.31	1.00
Sudan II	$Y = 5.96X + 0.09$	0.18	0.34	1.00
Sudan III	$Y = 7.67X - 0.25$	0.35	0.41	0.99
Sudan IV	$Y = 6.17X - 0.27$	0.29	0.34	0.99

The repeatability and intermediate precision were calculated for a spiked concentration of 100 µg/ml of a mixture of Sudan dyes. The samples were analyzed 6 times within a day and also between two days. The %R.S.D. values were coming within 2.0 which are accepted as per AOAC peer verified methods programme¹⁵. Before calculating the %R.S.D. values, homogeneity of variance test was conducted at 95% Confidence Interval. The *p* values (probability of making Type 1 error) were found to be >0.05. Besides, *p* value >0.05 obtained by performing one-way ANOVA¹⁷ also confirms the repeatability and intermediate precision (Table 2).

Table 2. Repeatability and intermediate precision for a concentration of 100 µg/ml spiked in a sample of chilli powder

Analyte	S.D.	<i>p</i> -values at 95% C.I.		%R.S.D.
		Homogeneity variance	I-way ANOVA	
Sudan I	1.07	1.00	0.61	1.05
Sudan II	1.88	0.77	0.67	1.88
Sudan III	1.56	0.74	0.10	1.57
Sudan IV	1.78	0.8	0.88	1.81

Reproducibility was evaluated by analyzing a spiked sample (100 µg/g) by three different analysts. Each experiment was an average of three replicates. The reproducibility data also was confirmed by conducting homogeneity variance test and one-way ANOVA which gave *p* values >0.05¹⁷ (Table 3).

The sensitivity of the method was evaluated by spiking each Sudan dye in a concentration of 0.6 µg/g (limit

Table 3. Reproducibility for a concentration of 100 µg/ml spiked in a sample of chilli powder

Analyte	S.D.	<i>p</i> -values at 95% C.I.		%R.S.D.
		Homogeneity variance	I-way ANOVA	
Sudan I	1.78	0.13	0.87	1.76
Sudan II	2.31	0.14	0.09	2.31
Sudan III	2.37	0.73	0.94	2.39
Sudan IV	2.62	0.07	0.33	2.64

of quantification) in five samples of chilli powder. The recoveries were found to be 93%, 93%, 92% and 93% respectively for Sudan I, II, III and IV and corresponding %R.S.D. values were 6.6, 6.4, 6.5 and 6.6 which is accepted for this level of concentration by AOAC peer verified methods programme.

The applicability of the method was evaluated by spiking each Sudan dye in different chilli products in different concentrations and calculated the %R.S.D. which is coming less than 2.0. This shows that the method is applicable in presence of common interfering agents (carotenoid pigments like capsanthin, capsorubin, β-carotene etc.) found in spice products. Recovery study of different amounts of Sudan dyes spiked in samples of pickle, chilli powder, tomato sauce and chill sauce were performed. All measurements were the average of 3 experiments. Percent recoveries ranged from 90 to 106% and were not influenced by the food matrix or the amount of dyes added (Table 4). Results obtained for different foods showed

Table 4. Recovery of Sudan dyes added to various food products

Sl. no.	Product ^a	Analyte spiked (µg/ml)				Recovered (µg/ml)				% Recovery			
		Sudan I	Sudan II	Sudan III	Sudan IV	Sudan I	Sudan II	Sudan III	Sudan IV	Sudan I	Sudan II	Sudan III	Sudan IV
		1.	Chilli powder-1	50	50	50	50	45	48	46	48	90	96
2.	Chill powder-5	100	100	100	100	96	98	95	106	96	98	95	106
3.	Chilli powder-3	250	250	250	250	245	248	250	253	98	99	100	101
4.	Pickle-1	50	50	50	50	49	48	50	52	98	96	100	104
5.	Pickle-2	100	100	100	100	98	97	104	98	98	97	104	98
6.	Pickle-3	250	250	250	250	250	241	245	243	100	96	98	97
7.	Tomato sauce-1	50	50	50	50	48	47	49	50	96	94	98	100
8.	Tomato sauce-2	100	100	100	100	95	92	91	96	95	92	91	92
9.	Tomato sauce-3	250	250	250	250	240	242	246	243	96	97	98	97
10.	Chilli sauce-1	50	50	50	50	45	47	50	48	90	94	100	96
11.	Chilli sauce-2	100	100	100	100	97	98	106	99	97	98	106	99
12.	Chilli sauce-3	250	250	250	250	240	240	242	241	96	96	97	96

^aThe samples were procured from local supermarkets and pre-examined for the absence of Sudan I-IV dyes.

Table 5. Recovery of spiked Sudan dyes at two conc. levels from different food matrices to show no matrix effect

Analyte	Analyte conc. spiked ($\mu\text{g/g}$)	Analyte recovered from different food matrices								<i>p</i> -values at 95% C.I.	
		Chilli sauce		Tomato sauce		Pickle		Chilli powder		Homogeneity variance	1-way ANOVA
		Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.		
Sudan I	20	20.8	2.4	19.6	1.8	19.8	1.5	19.2	0.8	0.33	0.52
	50	49.8	3.0	52.6	4.5	53	2.4	52	3.5	0.82	0.49
Sudan II	20	21.4	2.1	20.8	1.1	21.4	1.7	19.6	1.5	0.55	0.29
	50	52.4	1.9	49.8	4.9	51	4.3	49.6	2.7	0.41	0.61
Sudan III	20	19.2	0.8	19.8	2.4	20.2	2.9	21.8	1.9	0.41	0.29
	50	52.8	2.5	51	2.9	51.8	4.4	51.8	3.1	0.86	0.86
Sudan IV	20	20.2	1.3	20.2	0.8	21.8	2.6	20.2	1.1	0.2	0.33
	50	49.2	2.2	52.4	4.4	53.2	4.4	53	4	0.72	0.35

that no loss of dye was induced by the extraction and clarification steps. Furthermore, *p* values >0.05 obtained by conducting homogeneity of variance and one-way ANOVA [Kiemele *et al.*, 1999] also confirm that there is no matrix effect (Table 5).

After validation, the method was tried in the case of real samples (Fig. 3). Among the market samples investigated, one sample of chilli powder was found to contain Sudan I and Sudan IV in a concentration of 23 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 250 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ respectively (Table 6).

Conclusions :

A rapid and reliable HPLC method with gradient elu-

Table 6. Quantitative analysis of Sudan dyes in a commercial sample of chilli powder (*n* = 4)

Analyte	Sudan I ($\mu\text{g/g}$)	Sudan II ($\mu\text{g/g}$)	Sudan III ($\mu\text{g/g}$)	Sudan IV ($\mu\text{g/g}$)
Mean	23	n.d	n.d	250
S.D.	2.16	n.d	n.d	3.56

n.d. - not detected.

tion for the qualitative and quantitative analysis of Sudan dyes was established. Sample preparation and extraction is also simple irrespective of the food matrices. The quantification of all the four Sudan dyes is possible simultaneously in a single run. The method is validated for its accuracy, precision, limit of detection and limit of quan-

Fig. 3. HPLC chromatogram of a sample of chilli powder (market sample) containing Sudan I and Sudan IV analysed with variable wavelength detector at 491 nm and using C18 column. (MAU - Million Absorption Unit).

tification. The method can be applied for a routine analysis of chilli and chilli products for the presence of these dyes.

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